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Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz

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Tadqiqot LLC the city of Tashkent,

Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.

Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz

Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

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Mustafakulov Ishnazar Boynazarovich

Samarkand State Medical University

Samarkand branch of RNCEMP

Mustafakulov@mail.ru

Mamaradjabov Sobirzhon Ergashevich

Samarkand State Medical University

Samarkand branch of RNCEMP

Mustafakulov@mail.ru

Juraeva Zilola Aramovna

Samarkand State Medical University

Samarkand branch of RNCEMP

Mustafakulov@mail.ru

CURRENT STATUS AND PROBLEMS OF DIAGNOSTICS AND TREATMENT IN COMBINED ABDOMINAL INJURY

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ABSTRACT

There have been analyzed the results of modern literature, devoted to diagnostics and treatment of combined traumas of the abdomen and their prognosis. The main literary findings of home and foreign authors have been presented during the past years. The syndrome of mutual aggravation of injuries resulting from multiple trauma leads to a significant increase in the overall severity of the victim's condition. To determine the timing of each stage of CFT treatment and reduce the number of complications, we developed and introduced into clinical practice an algorithm for providing care for this injury. The tactics of treating patients with CTP, according to the developed algorithm, has an undeniable advantage over the previously used one - the percentage of inflammatory complications is reduced to a minimum: from 17% to 1.5%. Such an integrated approach increases the importance of triage of victims in order to achieve a therapeutic effect.

Keywords: combined abdominal trauma, ultrasound diagnostics, paracentesis, concomitant abdominal injury, ultrasound diagnostics, laparocentesis, conservative management, abdominal trauma, prognostic criteria, diagnostic laparotomy, hemorrhagic shock, damage control

Мустафакулов Ишназар Бойназарович

Самаркандский Государственный медицинский университет

Самаркандский филиал РНЦЭМП

Mustafakulov@mail.ru

Мамараджабов Собиржон Эргашевич

Самаркандский Государственный медицинский университет

Самаркандский филиал РНЦЭМП

Mustafakulov@mail.ru

Джураева Зилола Арамовна
Самаркандский Государственный медицинский университет
Самаркандский филиал РНЦЭМП
Mustafakulov@mail.ru

НЫНЕШНЕЕ СОСТОЯНИЕ И ПРОБЛЕМНЫЕ ВОПРОСЫ ДИАГНОСТИКИ И ТАКТИКИ ЛЕЧЕНИЯ ПРИ СОЧЕТАННОЙ АБДОМИНАЛЬНОЙ ТРАВМЕ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье представлены результаты изучения современной литературы о диагностике и лечении тяжелой сочетанной травмы живота и их прогнозирование. Авторами приведены основные литературные данные отечественных и зарубежных авторов за последнее десятилетие. Синдром взаимного отягощения повреждений, возникающий в результате множественной травмы, приводит к значительному увеличению общей тяжести состояния пострадавшего. Для определения времени каждого из этапов лечения ЦФТ, снижения количества осложнений нами был разработан и внедрен в клиническую практику алгоритм оказания помощи при данной травме. Тактика лечения пациентов с ЦФТ, согласно разработанного алгоритма, имеет несомненное преимущество перед ранее применявшейся - процент воспалительных осложнений сведен к минимальному: с 17% до 1,5%. Такой комплексный подход повышает важность сортировки пострадавших в целях достижения лечебного эффекта

Ключевые слова: сочетанная абдоминальная травма, ультразвуковая диагностика, лапароскопия, консервативное ведение, абдоминальная травма, прогностические критерии, диагностика лапаротомия, геморрагический шок, дежурный контроль, синдром ванка-станка

Mustafoqulov Ishnazar Boynazarovich

Samarqand davlat tibbiyot universiteti
RNCMP Samarqand filiali
Mustafakulov@mail.ru

Mamaradjabov Sobirjon Ergashevich

Samarqand davlat tibbiyot universiteti
RNCMP Samarqand filiali
Mustafakulov@mail.ru

Juraeva Zilola Aramovna

Samarqand davlat tibbiyot universiteti
RNCMP Samarqand filiali

QORIN BO'SHLIG'INING KOMBINATSIYALANGAN SHIKASTLANISHIDA DIAGNOSTIKA VA DAVOLASHNING HOZIRGI HOLATI VA MUAMMOLARI

ANNOTATSIYA

Qorin bo'shlig'ining qo'shma travmalarini diagnostika qilish va davolashga bag'ishlangan zamonaviy adabiyotlar natijalari va ularning prognozi tahlil qilindi. O'tgan yillar davomida mahalliy va xorijiy mualliflarning asosiy adabiy topilmalari taqdim etildi. Ko'p jarohatlar natijasida kelib chiqqan jarohatlarning o'zaro og'irlashuvi sindromi jabrlanuvchining ahvolidagi umumiy og'irligining sezilarli darajada oshishiga olib keladi. CFT davolashning har bir bosqichining vaqtini aniqlash va asoratlarni kamaytirish uchun biz ushbu jarohatni davolash algoritmini ishlab chiqdik va klinik amaliyotga kiritdik. CTP bilan og'rigan bemorlarni davolash taktikasi, ishlab chiqilgan algoritmgacha ko'ra, ilgari ishlatilganidan shubhasiz afzalliklarga ega - yallig'lanish asoratlari ulushi minimal darajaga tushiriladi: 17% dan 1,5% gacha. Bunday integratsiyalashgan yondashuv terapevtik ta'sirga erishish uchun jabrlanuvchilarni triyajning ahamiyatini oshiradi.

Kalit so'zlar: qorin bo'shlig'ining kombinatsiyalangan shikastlanishi, ultratovush diagnostikasi, parasentez. qorin bo'shlig'ining birgalikdagi shikastlanishi, ultratovush diagnostikasi, laparosentez, konservativ davolash, qorin bo'shlig'i shikastlanishi, prognostik mezonlar, diagnostik laparotomiya,

gemorragik shok, zararni nazorat qilish

Introduction: In recent years, there has been a steady increase in injuries worldwide. Man-made and natural disasters, local military conflicts, transport and industrial accidents in 50-60% of all injuries lead to combined and multiple damage to organs and systems of the human body, and, as a result, to high sanitary losses in the first hours and days [1, 2,3]. Combined injury is a simultaneous damage to two or more of the seven anatomical regions of the body by one traumatic agent. Among the causes of deaths from injuries, concomitant injuries account for more than 60%, although they account for 8-10% of inpatients with injuries [4,18,19,].

Abdominal injuries account for 1.5 to 36.5% of peacetime injuries, but their frequency and severity continue to increase [5,6,]. According to Tulupov A.N., [16]. in severe concomitant trauma, injuries of the abdominal organs are present in almost 30% of the victims. Such an injury, due to the severity of damage to internal organs and the difficulties of diagnosis, is characterized by a high rate of complications and mortality, which, according to various authors, ranges from 25 to 65%. With an isolated injury of one abdominal organ, mortality ranges from 5.1 to 20.4%, and with a combined injury, from 18.3 to 64% [7,8,9,].

Closed abdominal injuries are accompanied by a large number of complications and high mortality due to diagnostic difficulties and frequent combination with injuries to other organs and systems [10]. A special problem is the diagnosis and treatment of concomitant closed trauma of the abdominal organs, accompanied by shock. Hospital mortality in this variant of pathology ranges from 17.3 to 72.7% [13,14,]. For example, over the past 5 years, mortality from traffic accidents in Russia has increased by 65%, and the number of deaths reaches 33-35 thousand people per year [11,12,].

There are several terms in the literature that define multiple injuries of various areas of the body in severe trauma. In the domestic literature, the term severe concomitant injury (TST) is most often used. However, in the big medical encyclopedia there is the following definition: polytrauma - simultaneous damage to several anatomical regions in one victim.

Combined damage is the simultaneous damage to several different systems or organs. TST as a model of an extreme condition is damage to two or more anatomical regions of the body. Combined injury, by which we mean simultaneous damage to two or more of the seven anatomical regions of the body, is a complex multifactorial and severe form of injury, manifested by numerous pathological syndromes, accompanied by a frequent change in the dominant factor, a large number of complications and high mortality. In the diagnosis, the authors recommend indicating the leading lesion [15,16,17]. A distinctive feature of TST is the phenomenon of mutual aggravation of damage. Each of the local injuries is not associated with a threat to life, but their combination really creates such a threat. The role of each factor is determined not so much by the total number of lesions, but by the simultaneous coexistence of several lesions, i.e. a life-threatening injury comes to the fore, which, together with other injuries, is fraught with the threat of developing a state of shock with subsequent death [20].

According to the WHO, injuries today rank third among the causes of general mortality of the population, and in the group of people under 45 years of age, it firmly holds the first place. TST is a big problem not only for surgery, anesthesiology and resuscitation, but also social [21]. In the United States, trauma is the number one cause of death in the under 35 age group, accounting for 50% and the third leading cause of hospitalization in US hospitals.

Severe combined injury accounts for 26.6-80% of all types of injuries [22]. In 82% of the victims, it was the result of an accident, in 9% it was a fall from a height, in 6% it was an industrial injury, and in 3% it was a domestic injury [23]. Combined injuries of the chest and abdominal organs in most cases are accompanied by shock, and in 64.4% - severe. The dominant injury among them is TBI - 72.2%; trauma of the lower extremities is 67.8%, abdominal trauma - 43.9%, chest trauma - 39.4%, upper limbs - 32.1%, pelvis - 26.6% [24,25,].

Mortality from trauma has the following structure: in half of the cases, death occurs immediately, in 30% of cases - within a few hours after the injury. At the same time, 80% of the victims die at the prehospital stage. Mortality in some injuries reaches 70-80% [26]. Mortality of

victims with a combination of TBI, lung injury and heart contusion reaches 100% [27]. According to foreign authors [22,23,] out of all injured patients undergoing hospital treatment, polytrauma was recorded in 9-15% of cases, including 70-75% in young and middle-aged people. In 75% of the victims, multiple injuries of the musculoskeletal system were observed, in the rest - various injuries of internal organs, more often the brain, combined with fractures of the bones of the extremities.

The injuries that make up polytrauma most often aggravate each other. Shock occurs in 21% of patients with multiple fractures, and in 57% of patients with combined injuries [11].

After recovery from shock, patients with polytrauma often remain in a serious condition for a long time, due to massive blood loss and impaired activity of organs and systems. The main causes of death in injuries: TBI - 34.2%, shock - 24%, a combination of these causes - 10.1%, fat embolism - 5.1%, acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS) - 2.6%. According to a number of authors, traumatic shock caused by massive trauma to organs and tissues, even without large blood loss, can lead to severe perfusion disorders of organs and tissues, systemic inflammatory response syndrome, and multiple organ failure. Lethality in massive tissue damage is 47.6%, and in multiple injuries - 64%. Among trauma survivors, 35.5-40.9% become disabled [23,24].

Injuries are a top priority in any society, and addressing them adequately in the future must play a central role in the health system. Today, in industrialized countries, injury is the leading cause of death in people under the age of 40 [25,26]. In Germany in 2019, only as a result of transport accidents, the death rate per 100 thousand of the population was 3.8, in Russia - 12, in England - 3.2. In Ukraine, due to injuries, the death rate per 100 thousand of the population was 10.2. In the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2019, the death rate from injuries in road traffic accidents per 100 thousand of the population was 11.7, in 2018 - 11.5 [24].

More than 50% of those injured are under the age of 40, which causes significant medical and social problems, as well as huge economic losses. In Germany, the total economic cost of treating injuries following accidents is estimated at DM 23.1 billion per year. In the United States, the annual cost of inpatient treatment for trauma victims is estimated at no less than \$11 billion. Half of these costs and about $\frac{3}{4}$ of the cost of a hospital stay are for isolated injuries, 25% of the costs fall on severe injuries that require treatment in specialized trauma centers. In England, economic losses due to fatal injuries are estimated at 2.2 billion pounds, which is 1% of national production [12,23,].

Both in foreign and domestic literature there are different approaches to the classifications of concomitant injury.

Modern classifications of multiple and associated traumavary diverse based on the nature and severity of the damage. Others [17] recommend distributing victims with concomitant injury according to the principle of matching tactics to the dominant injury.

There are several terms in the literature that define multiple injuries of various areas of the body in severe trauma. In the domestic literature, the term severe concomitant injury (TST) is most often used. However, in the big medical encyclopedia there is the following definition: polytrauma - simultaneous damage to several anatomical regions in one victim.

Combined damage is the simultaneous damage to several different systems or organs. TST as a model of an extreme condition is damage to two or more anatomical regions of the body. According to V.E. Rozanova (1999), "Concomitant injury, by which we mean simultaneous damage to two or more of the seven anatomical regions of the body, is a complex multifactorial and severe form of traumatic injury, manifested by numerous pathological syndromes, accompanied by a frequent change in the dominant factor, a large number of complications and high mortality". In the diagnosis, the author recommends indicating the leading lesion [19]. A distinctive feature of TST is the phenomenon of mutual aggravation of damage. Each of the local injuries is not associated with a threat to life, but their combination really creates such a threat. The role of each factor is determined not so much by the total number of lesions, but by the simultaneous coexistence of several lesions, i.e. the functional component comes to the fore, the interaction, which is realized in functional damage [18].

According to the WHO, injuries today rank third among the causes of general mortality of the population, and in the group of people under 45 years of age, it firmly holds the first place. TST is a

big problem not only in surgery, anesthesiology and resuscitation, but also social [19]. In the US, trauma ranks first as a cause of death in the age group under 35 years old and accounts for 50%, it is the third most common cause of hospitalization in US hospitals [10,22,].

Severe concomitant injury accounts for 26.6-80% of all types of injuries [24,28,]. In 82% of the victims, it was the result of an accident, 9% - a fall from a height, 6% had an industrial injury, and 3% - a domestic injury. Combined injuries of the chest and abdomen are always accompanied by shock, and in 64.4% - severe. The dominant injury among them is TBI - 72.2%; trauma of the lower extremities is 67.8%, abdominal trauma - 43.9%, chest trauma - 39.4%, upper limbs - 32.1%, pelvis - 26.6%.

Mortality from trauma has the following structure: in half of the cases, death occurs immediately, in 30% of cases - within a few hours after the injury. At the same time, 80% of the victims die at the prehospital stage. Mortality in some injuries reaches 70-80% [13,17,]. Mortality of victims with a combination of TBI, lung injury and heart contusion reaches 100% [16]. According to the CITO data, out of all injured patients undergoing inpatient treatment, polytrauma was recorded in 9-15% of cases, including 70-75% in young and middle-aged people. According to Rossaint R, Bouillon B, [21], combined injuries account for 40-60% of all injuries. In 75% of the victims, multiple injuries of the musculoskeletal system were observed, in the rest - various injuries of internal organs, more often the brain, combined with fractures of the bones of the extremities.

The injuries that make up polytrauma most often aggravate each other. With multiple fractures, shock occurs in 21%, with combined injuries - in 57% of the victims [7].

After recovery from shock, patients with polytrauma often remain in a serious condition for a long time, due to massive blood loss and impaired activity of organs and systems. The main causes of death in injuries: TBI - 34.2%, shock - 24%, a combination of these causes - 10.1%, fat embolism - 5.1%, acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS) - 2.6%. According to F.S. Glumcher et al. (2002), traumatic shock caused by massive trauma to organs and tissues, even without large blood loss, can lead to severe perfusion disorders of organs and tissues, systemic inflammatory response syndrome and multiple organ failure. Lethality in case of massive tissue damage is 47.6%, and in case of multiple injuries it is 64% [21,26]. Among survivors after an injury, 35.5-40.9% become disabled [9].

Injuries are a top priority in any society, and addressing them adequately in the future must play a central role in the health system. Today, in industrialized countries, injury is the leading cause of death in people under the age of 40 [8]. In the Federal Republic of Germany (FRG) in 1994, 9896 people died only as a result of traffic accidents, in Russia - 36000, in England - 18000 [18], in Ukraine 27494 people died due to injuries in 1993, in 1995 - 30965 people. In the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2006, 2393 people died from injuries in traffic accidents, in 2008 - 2731.

More than 50% of those injured are under the age of 40, which causes significant medical and social problems, as well as huge economic losses. In Germany, the total economic costs of treating injuries after accidents are estimated at 23.1 billion DM per year. In the United States in 1985, the annual cost of clinical treatment of the injured was estimated at 11 billion dollars. Half of these costs and about $\frac{3}{4}$ of the cost of a hospital stay are for isolated injuries, 25% of the costs fall on severe injuries that require treatment in specialized trauma centers. In England, economic losses due to fatal injuries are estimated at 2.2 billion pounds, which is 1% of national production [21,23,].

Today, injuries are the leading cause of death for people under the age of 40. In the first place among the causes of mortality are cardiovascular diseases, in the second place are malignant diseases, in the third place are injuries, but the average age of deaths from cardiovascular diseases is 79 years, from oncological diseases - 68.6 years. The average age of those who died from injuries was 34.4 years [19].

Mortality from injuries among people under 40 years of age is higher than from cardiovascular and oncological diseases, and the occupancy of trauma beds is greater than the number of beds for cardiological and oncological patients. High mortality in combined and multiple injuries is associated with the severity of damage to internal organs, retroperitoneal organs, brain, limbs, as well as early and late complications that are observed in 50% of victims. Disability due to polytrauma reaches 28-

50%, and its main cause is damage to the musculoskeletal system [5].

Method and materials: One of the urgent medical and social problems is associated injury, which, due to the intensity of production, the rapid growth of transport and construction, is increasing in all economically developed countries in terms of frequency and severity of injuries. Combined trauma belongs to the exciting sections of surgical activity, which includes a palette of surgical science and surgical therapy from wound treatment to pathophysiological studies, microcirculation and ventilation disorders, including acute surgery of organs and limbs. And finally, the diagnosis and emergency treatment of intracranial hemorrhages.

Combined injury is a simultaneous damage to two or more of the seven anatomical regions of the body (brain and spinal cord, bones of the skeleton and soft tissues of the limbs, internal organs of the chest and abdomen, pelvis, spine) in various combinations by one traumatic agent.

All types of combined injuries, with a focus on the leading injury, can be assigned to one of seven groups: group 1 - combined craniocerebral injury, group 2 - combined spinal cord injury, group 3 - combined chest injury, 4th group - combined trauma of the abdomen and retroperitoneal organs, 5th group - combined trauma of the musculoskeletal system, 6th group - combined trauma of two or more cavities, 7th group - combined trauma without leading injury.

The allocation of polytrauma to a separate category is important due to certain features of such injuries, which should be taken into account when sorting and providing medical care. The frequency of damage to certain areas of the body with combined gunshot wounds and closed injuries, according to I.A. Yeryukhin and V.I. Khrupkina (2002), respectively, is: the head - 29.4 and 70.6%; neck - 1.3 and 0%; chest - 32.4 and 40.7%; stomach - 58.1 and 27.4%; pelvis - 36.8 and 32.2%; spine - 5.9 and 11.3%; limbs - 74.4 and 66.2%). Since several areas are damaged simultaneously with a combined injury, the overall result is much higher than 100%.

From a practical point of view, for general surgeons, the 4th group is of greatest interest - a combined injury of the abdomen and retroperitoneal organs. The leading ones are injuries of the parenchymal organs of the abdomen, mainly the liver and spleen, mesenteric vessels, accompanied by bleeding into the abdominal cavity, followed by trauma to hollow organs, primarily the large and small intestines, the bladder with the release of their contents into the abdominal cavity and the development of peritonitis [5].

Damage to the organs of the retroperitoneal space is much less common - ruptures of the kidney, pancreas, duodenum and extraperitoneal part of the colon [3,5].

Leading injuries, which are characterized by bleeding into the abdominal cavity, account for more than 85% of all abdominal injuries, injuries of hollow organs - more than 15%.

In the first case, the victims have a classic picture of hypovolemic (hemorrhagic) shock, in the second - peritoneal symptoms of varying severity, depending on the localization and extent of intestinal damage. Shock hypotension in comparison with trauma of parenchymal organs in case of damage to hollow organs is much less pronounced and is relatively easily stopped in the early period of injury.

Results: Abdominal injuries account for 1.5 to 18% of all peacetime injuries, but their frequency and severity continue to increase.

Closed abdominal injuries are accompanied by a large number of complications and high mortality due to diagnostic difficulties and frequent combination with injuries to other organs and systems [2]. The diagnostic algorithm, from our point of view, should be considered towards the maximum use of modern low-traumatic and highly informative diagnostic methods. Mortality in isolated trauma of one organ ranges from 5.1 to 20.4%, in combined injuries - from 18.3 to 64%. As a rule, open injuries are not accompanied by such severe injuries of internal organs and retroperitoneal organs as closed ones, and their mortality rate is 10-25%.

Stab-cut wounds of the anterior abdominal wall penetrate into the abdominal cavity in almost 70% of the victims, but damage to the internal organs was noted in approximately every fourth of them.

Gunshot wounds are penetrating in 80-90% of victims, and the frequency of damage to internal

organs reaches 75-80% [3].

With a closed injury, the stomach is least likely to be injured, but with penetrating stab wounds, the frequency reaches 19%, and patients usually die not from this cause, but from concomitant (combined) injuries.

Diagnosis and treatment of injuries of the duodenum (duodenum) remains one of the most difficult and not fully resolved problems of emergency surgery. With isolated injuries of the duodenum, mortality is 11.8-30.5%, and with combined 46.6-80.0% [2]. Diagnostic and tactical errors in assisting victims with duodenal injuries often lead to the development of life-threatening complications in the early postoperative period, the frequency of which ranges from 25.0 to 72.5% and high mortality. In cases of development of retroperitoneal phlegmon, lethality can reach 100%. High lethality is due to the failure of the sutures, post-traumatic pancreatitis and the development of purulent complications - retroperitoneal phlegmon, peritonitis and sepsis. In recent years, there has been a trend towards an increase in the frequency of damage to the duodenum,

To date, there are no unified approaches to determining the nature and extent of surgical intervention for damage to the duodenum. Some authors recommend limiting themselves to applying a two-row suture to the duodenal defect, others supplement the primary suture with stomach-draining operations. A number of surgeons prefer operations to "turn off" the duodenum, and in some cases they resort to its resection, or use a serous-muscular-submucosal flap of the greater curvature of the stomach on a vascular pedicle to cover the duodenal suture line.

The greatest difficulties in timely diagnosis are observed in cases of damage to the retroperitoneal part of the duodenum, which are not diagnosed in 10-30% of the victims.

Damage to the duodenum is also quite rare (1.4-5%), which are difficult to diagnose, especially with retroperitoneal ruptures. Mortality in isolated injuries of the duodenum ranges from 12.5 to 26%, with combined injuries it reaches 50-80%.

Damage to the pancreas is 6.4-12%, and in the vast majority are combined. Mortality averages 18%, with extensive lesions of the organ exceeds 70% [4].

Most authors, when assessing the thanatogenesis of trauma, give priority to traumatic shock, considering it to be the main and predominant in patients with concomitant trauma.

In fact, traumatic shock, as a manifestation of acute blood loss, is observed in approximately 60% of victims. In the remaining patients, acute respiratory disorders come to the fore as a result of damage to the brain and spinal cord or damage to the external respiration apparatus in case of chest injury.

The main cause of shock is extracranial damage, accompanied by significant blood loss. At the same time, there is a large lability of vital signs in almost all victims with concomitant trauma complicated by shock. It is recommended in the treatment of patients with shock in polytrauma, along with anti-shock measures, to solve diagnostic problems as quickly as possible through the widespread use of X-ray studies, laparoscopy, "groping catheter", diagnostic punctures, ultrasound scanning, etc. The choice, volume and sequence of the diagnostic program is determined the nature of the suspected injuries and the condition of the victim.

Combinations of various circulatory and respiratory disorders of both central and peripheral genesis are not uncommon, which gives reason to talk about the syndrome of mutual burdening.

One of the causes of mortality in combined trauma of the abdomen is damage to large vessels, the frequency of which reaches 2.2% with a closed injury, and 3.8% with gunshot wounds. Of the 51 victims with abdominal trauma with damage to the large vessels of the abdominal cavity, 29 (56.6%) died. Surgical treatment in full, according to the authors, should be carried out only after stabilization of hemodynamics. From our point of view, with continued bleeding and a critical condition of the victim, it is necessary to use techniques and methods for temporarily stopping bleeding by open or endosurgical methods (clamping of the vascular pedicle of the spleen and hepatoduodenal ligament, clipping of the mesenteric vessels, compression of large main vessels or abdominal aorta, etc.).

All mortality in polytrauma is divided into three large groups - immediate death within seconds or minutes, the nearest - within the first three hours, and late - over three hours from the moment of injury. Of the dead, up to 80% die immediately at the scene or in the next three hours in a hospital,

and only 20% during various periods of traumatic illness.

Death within the first three hours accounts for 30% of deaths from concomitant trauma. For the victims of the fourth group with combined abdominal injuries, the cause of death was hemoperitoneum due to ruptures of the liver and spleen, retroperitoneal hematomas with multiple fractures of the pelvis and ruptures of the kidneys.

Hemoperitoneum is an unconditional indication for surgical intervention.

Operations for bleeding into the abdominal cavity account for over 90% of all operations for bleeding of any localization. The volume of hemoperitoneum is an important prognostic sign: if it is less than 2 liters, the prognosis is favorable, from 2 to 3 liters - mortality is 50-60%, from 3 to 3.5 liters - only a few survive. With hemoperitoneum with a volume of about 4 liters, all patients die on the operating table or in the immediate postoperative period [2,3,].

In a period of more than 3 days, death from pneumonia, intoxication and sepsis 72.7%, fat embolism - 7.2%, thromboembolism - 7.2% comes to the fore. Actually surgical causes (failure of sutures of the gastrointestinal tract, peritonitis, etc.) occupy a small place in the structure of early mortality - less than 1%.

Many authors note a high frequency of various types of errors and defects in the diagnosis and treatment of injuries. Untimely recognition during life of damage that leads to death, according to LM Geeraedts et al. (2005), M. A. Schreiber et al. (2005) is 12.9%, and late diagnosis is 3.4%.

The data of the literature testify that the "vain" laparotomy, performed for diagnostic purposes, with an unmotivated refusal to carry out the program of examination of the victims, still has a large proportion. If such interventions in emergency abdominal surgery or in isolated injuries are a large but tolerable act of unreasonable surgical aggression, then with combined injuries they can often end fatally.

The sequence of performing two or more emergency surgical interventions in one patient causes a lively discussion. In most cases, many surgeons adhere to the tactics of sequential interventions, in accordance with their degree of urgency. We share the point of view that simultaneous operations performed during "one anesthesia" (stopping intraperitoneal bleeding, decompression craniotomy, elimination of spinal cord compression, fixation of pelvic bones in case of Malgenya fractures, skeletal traction and other combinations) should take place. Everything depends on the severity and shockogenicity of the injury, the initial state of the victim, his age and the presence of concomitant pathology, the prognosis for the development of complications of each injury and the overall assessment of the degree of surgical aggression.

Thus, the analysis of the scientific literature shows that the problem of choosing the scope of surgical intervention in patients with severe concomitant abdominal trauma against the background of traumatic and hemorrhagic shock still remains unresolved.

Despite the fact that in the scientific literature for many years reports a significant risk of surgery for shock, the vast majority many surgeons continue to use traditional tactics radically to eliminate all damage to the organs of the chest and abdominal cavity, regardless of the severity of the victim's condition.

Conclusions.

1. One of the pathogenetic factors in the development of a traumatic disease, which are observed already in the first hours after an injury, is homeostasis disturbances - traumatic shock and acute blood loss.

2. It is a matter of serious concern that over the past 10 years, despite the success of fundamental and applied sciences, the emergence of new theoretical concepts in explaining the pathogenesis of traumatic and extra-abdominal complications, traumatic shock and acute blood loss are still the main causes of death in patients.

3. Despite a number of positive reviews from surgeons using the "damage control" tactics, this direction in our country (RUz) has been actively developing over the past years, which has been the subject of a number of works in the emergency medical care system.

4. An important component in the structure of the problem of combined abdominal injuries is

the assessment of the severity of damage using various scales.

References

1. Мустафакулов И. Б. и др. SURGICAL TACTICS IN CASE OF ISOLATED INJURIES OF SMALL AND LARGE INTESTINE //УЗБЕКСКИЙ МЕДИЦИНСКИЙ ЖУРНАЛ. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 2.
2. Курбонов Н. А. и др. MODERN APPROACHES TO THE TREATMENT OF DEEP BURNING PATIENTS //УЗБЕКСКИЙ МЕДИЦИНСКИЙ ЖУРНАЛ. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 2.
3. Erkinovich K. Y. METHODS OF EARLY SURGICAL TREATMENT OF BURNS //Central Asian Research Journal for Interdisciplinary Studies (CARJIS). – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. Special Issue 4. – pp. 184-188.
4. Shakirov B. M., Avazov A. A., Khursanov E. E. COMPLEX TREATMENT OF PATIENTS WITH EXTENSIVE DEEP BURNS OF THE LOWER LIMB // Stroke. - 2017. - Т. 48. - pp. 2318-2325.
5. Akhmedov R. F. et al. Diagnostic significance of the level of procalcitonin in burn disease // Journal of Emergency Surgery. I. Dzhanlidze. – 2021. – no. S1. -pp. 11-12.
6. Akhmedov R. F. et al. Our experience in the treatment of burn sepsis // Journal of Emergency Surgery. I. Dzhanlidze. – 2021. – no. S1. - pp. 10-11.
7. Shakirov B., Avazov A., Khursanov Y. COMPREHENSIVE TREATMENT OF PATIENTS WITH EXTENSIVE DEEP BURNS LOWER LIMBS. – 2022.
8. Mustafakulov I. B. et al. AMNIOTIC MEMBRANE-AS AN EFFECTIVE BIOLOGICAL WOUND COVERING // UZBEK MEDICAL JOURNAL. – 2021. – no. SPECIAL 1.
9. Mustafakulov I. B. et al. OPTIMIZATION OF INTENSIVE THERAPY FOR BURN SHOCK // UZBEK MEDICAL JOURNAL. – 2021. – no. SPECIAL 1.
10. Shakirov B. M., Avazov A. A., Khursanov E. E. COMPLEX TREATMENT OF PATIENTS WITH EXTENSIVE DEEP BURNS OF THE LOWER LIMB // Stroke. - 2017. - Т. 48. - pp. 2318-2325.
11. Usanov Zh. R. U. et al. Possibilities of diagnosis and treatment of acute severe pancreatitis // Bulletin of science and education. – 2021. – no. 3-2 (106). - pp. 103-106.
12. Avazov A. A. et al. PATHOGENESIS, CLINICS, PRINCIPLES OF TREATMENT OF BURN SHOCK // Bulletin of science and education. – 2021. – no. 3-2 (106). - pp. 99-102.
13. Daminov F. A. et al. Features of therapeutic nutrition for early prevention of gastrointestinal complications in burn patients // Journal of Emergency Surgery. I. Dzhanlidze. – 2021. – no. S1. – pp. 21-21.
14. Karabaev Kh.K. I. Dzhanlidze. – 2021. – no. S1. – pp. 28-29.
15. Daminov F. A. et al. Intestinal insufficiency syndrome and its correction in severely burned patients // Journal of Emergency Surgery. I. Dzhanlidze. – 2021. – no. S1. - pp. 20-21.
16. Avazov A. A. et al. ALLOPLASTIC HERNIOPLASTY IN STRENGTHENED VENTAL HERNIAS // Youth and medical science in the XXI century. - 2014. - pp. 536-537.
17. Shakirov B. M., Avazov A. A., Khursanov E. E. COMPLEX TREATMENT OF PATIENTS WITH EXTENSIVE DEEP BURNS OF THE LOWER LIMB // Stroke. - 2017. - Т. 48. - pp. 2318-2325.
18. Avazov A. A., Dzhumageldiev Sh. Sh., Islamov N. K. DIAGNOSTICS OF VARIOUS FORMS OF ACUTE PANCREATITIS // Youth and medical science in the XXI century. - 2014. - pp. 535-536.
19. Abdurakhmanovich A. A. et al. METHODS OF EARLY SURGICAL TREATMENT OF BURNS //Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal. - 2022. - Vol. 3. - No. 6. - pp. 528-532.
20. Ruziboev S. et al. TREATMENT OF ACUTE ADHESIVE INTESTINAL OBSTRUCTION WITH MINI-INVASIVE METHODS //InterConf. - 2021. - pp. 768-773.

21. Abduraxmanovich A. A. et al. POSSIBILITIES OF APPLYING MINIMALLY INVASIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN TREATMENT OF SEVERE ACUTE PANCREATITIS //CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF MEDICAL AND NATURAL SCIENCES. - 2021. - Vol. 2. - No. 3. - pp. 246-249.
22. Gulamov O. M. et al. Modern methods of diagnosis and treatment of barrett esophagus // Doctor's herald. - 2020. - T. 2. - P. 94.
23. Mukhammadiev M. et al. INDICATORS OF ORGAN DEFICIENCY DEVELOPMENT IN ACUTE PANCREATITIS // InterConf. - 2021. - pp. 738-753.
24. Avazov A. CLASSIFICATION OF FACTORS INFLUENCING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF PERSONNEL ACTIVITIES IN INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES //International Finance and Accounting. - 2019. - T. 2019. - No. 5. - P. 17.
25. Mustafakulov I. B. et al. SEVERE ASSOCIATED ABDOMINAL INJURY // Journal of hepato-gastroenterological research. - 2020. - Vol. 1. - No. one.
26. Mustafakulov I. B. et al. INTESTINAL INJURIES IN COMBINED ABDOMINAL TRAUMA // UZBEK MEDICAL JOURNAL. – 2021. – no. SPECIAL 1.
27. Mustafakulov I., Tagaev K., Umedov H. OUR EXPERIENCE IN THE TREATMENT OF PATIENTS WITH THERMO-INHALATION INJURY // Journal of Cardiorespiratory Research. - 2020. - Vol. 1. - No. 2. - pp. 53-58.
28. Mustafakulov I. B. Stomach Injury in Multiple and Polytrauma // American Journal of Medical Case Reports. - 2014. - Vol. 2. - No. 7. - pp. 133-135.
29. Mustafakulov I., Umedov H. MODERN TACTICAL APPROACHES IN THE TREATMENT OF TRAUMATIC LIVER INJURIES // Journal of hepato-gastroenterological research. - 2020. - Vol. 1. - No. 2. - pp. 48-51.
30. Mustafakuov I., Umedov H. INTRA-ABDOMINAL HYPERTENSION SYNDROME WITH COMBINED ABDOMINAL INJURIES // Journal of hepato-gastroenterological research. - 2020. - Vol. 1. - No. 2. - pp. 52-55.
31. Mustafakuov, Ishnazar, and Khushvakt Umedov. "SYNDROME OF INTRA-ABDOMINAL HYPERTENSION WITH COMBINED ABDOMINAL INJURIES." Journal of Hepato-Gastroenterological Research 1.2 (2020): 52-55.
32. Mustafakuov, I., & Umedov, H. (2020). SYNDROME OF INTRA-ABDOMINAL HYPERTENSION WITH COMBINED ABDOMINAL INJURIES. Journal of Hepato-Gastroenterological Research, 1(2), 52-55.
33. . Shakirov B. M., Avazov A. A., Umedov X. A. Peculiarities of hand burn treatment in the conditions of moist medium // ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science, 04 (108). - 2022. - pp. 289-291.

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Tadqiqot LLC the city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.

Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz

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Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000